

References

1. L. P. HAMMETT, "Physical Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1970.
2. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, "Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1968.
3. P. R. WEILS, "Liber Free Energy Relationships", Academic, London, 1968.
4. R. D. GILLIOM, "Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry" Addison-Wesley, Philippines, 1970, Chap. 9.
5. L. G. HEPNER and W. C. HARA, *J. Phys. Chem. (Ithaca)*, 1961, 65, 811.
6. J. W. LARSON and L. G. HEPNER in "Solute-solvent Interactions", eds. J. R. COETZEE and C. D. RITCHIE, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1969, Chap. 1.
7. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik. Chem. (NF)*, 1974, 88, 1.
8. W. I. BRIGHT and H. J. BRISCOE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 787.
9. D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Leipzig)* 1977, 259, 1097.
10. A. K. MONDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 495.
11. S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Physik. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1930, 261, 573.
12. J. HINE, "Structural Effects on Equilibria in Organic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1976, Chap. 3.
13. R. W. TAFT, E. PRICE, I. R. FOX, I. O. LEWIS, K. K. ANDERSON and G. T. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 709, 3146.
14. H. H. JAFFE and H. L. JONES, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 964.
15. H. HRDLJVIC, D. BELLUS and M. LAZAR, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 33, 59.
16. E. DE MEDICIS FRYTMANS and A. BRUYLANT, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 70, 10934.
17. M. J. S. DEWAR and P. J. GRIDALE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 3539.
18. R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3120, 1953, 75, 4231.
19. Y. OKAMATO and H. C. BROWN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 487.
20. N. B. CHAPMAN, A. ESHAN, J. SHORTER and K. J. TOYNE, *J. Chem. Soc., B*, 1967, 570, 1968, 178.
21. R. W. TAFT and I. O. LEWIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 5343.
22. R. W. TAFT in "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", ed. M. S. NEWMANN, Wiley, New York, 1956, Chap. 13.

Studies on *m*-Cresol - Formaldehyde Cationic Resins

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ION-exchange resins find wide range applications¹. Many of these resins are prepared from petroleum products, and attempts have been made to find out cheaper substitutes which retain all the properties of the parent resin. Vasudevan and Sharma² used sulphonated charcoal obtained from coconut shells and saw dust for the substitute. Phenol-formaldehyde was chosen as the polymeric matrix. They

showed that the substitution upto 30-35% does not lead to reduction in the chemical and thermal stability or the apparent exchange capacity for various ions. Based on this observation an attempt has been made to synthesise and study the properties of sulphonated *m*-cresol-formaldehyde, substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from *Bombox malabarica* fruit shell (considered as waste). *m*-Cresol was chosen to represent the phenol moiety as it appears to yield high cross-linking polymers.

Experimental

Concentrated H₂SO₄ (12.5 ml) was added slowly to *m*-cresol (10 ml) with constant cooling. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 h, then cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight. Concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to *Bombox malabarica* fruitshell and heated on a water-bath for ~6 h. Then it was washed free of acids and dried at 70°. Calculated quantity of the sulphonated charcoal was added to *m*-cresol-sulphuric acid so as to give percentage substitutions of 0, 10, 20, 30, 35, 40, 50 and 100. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70°, and the product ground, sieved and labelled as A, B, C, D, E, F, G and H.

Physical measurements: The absolute densities of the resin in the hydrated and dehydrated states were determined by using specific gravity bottle in water and in toluene (Table 1). The gravimetric percent swelling α was calculated from the equation,

$$\alpha = \frac{(M_w - M_d)}{M_d} \times 100$$

where, M_d and M_w are respectively the weight of dry and finally swollen resins. Swelling percentage for various samples are given in Table 1.

Attrition percentage: The percentage attrition of different samples was determined and compared with each other. The particles in each sample were separated into two sizes: > 200 and < 200 mesh. Particles greater than 200 mesh size were shaken for several hours, and again the particles greater than 200 mesh in size were separated. From the weights of the particles before and after shaking, the attrition effect was calculated for each sample, and the values were compared with each other. The percentage attrition of the composites are given in Table 1.

Exchange capacity: The exchange capacity of the samples for the exchange of Na^I, Mg^{II}, Zn^{II} and Ca^{II} ions on the H⁺-form of the exchange were determined. The samples were converted to H⁺-form, test columns prepared in graduated burettes with cotton-wool plugs, known weight of the sample was made into slurry with distilled water and the burette column filled with the slurry. A 0.1 M sodium sulphate solution (20 ml) was added slowly to the column and allowed to pass at the rate of

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2–3 ml min⁻¹; the effluent was collected. The H⁺ ions liberated was titrated with standard 0.1 N NaOH and the exchange capacity of the resins (meq g⁻¹) was calculated. The ion exchange resin was regenerated by washing with 4 N HCl (20 ml) and subsequently with distilled water until the effluent was free from chloride ions. A 0.1 N Ca^{II}/Zn^{II}/Mg^{II} solution (20 ml) was passed at the rate

Results and Discussions

The swelling percentages decrease from sample A to H; for pure resin the value is highest. This is due to the fact that when charcoal is added, the porous nature decreases and so also the swelling capacity. The absolute densities of the pure resin and the composites in the hydrated state are less

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE SWELLING, ABSOLUTE DENSITY, ATTRITION PERCENTAGE AND EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF DIFFERENT RESIN COMPOSITES

Sample	Shell charcoal in resin %	Average swelling %	Absolute density		Percentage attrition. The amount passed through 200 mesh sieve after shaking	Exchange column capacity, meq g ⁻¹			
			Hydrated state	Dehydrated state		Na ^I	Mg ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ca ^{II}
A	0	57.00	1.26	1.56	24.76	0.85	1.08	1.14	1.25
B	10	55.50	1.23	1.52	22.85	0.82	1.08	1.08	1.18
C	20	52.60	1.21	1.49	20.67	0.78	0.97	1.02	1.11
D	30	50.00	1.19	1.44	19.28	0.54	0.87	0.89	0.98
E	35	49.00	1.15	1.42	18.15	0.16	0.51	0.54	0.60
F	40	48.80	1.13	1.40	17.92	0.06	0.44	0.46	0.50
G	50	47.20	1.10	1.36	16.65	0.04	0.40	0.43	0.46
H	100	35.00	1.06	1.21	11.68	0.09	0.28	0.32	0.35

of 2–3 ml min⁻¹, the effluent collected and the unexchanged metal ion titrated against standard 0.1 M EDTA solution. The exchange capacity for the different cations was calculated (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of Ion-exchange capacity vs % charcoal: (●) Ca^{II}, (Δ) Zn^{II}, (□) Mg^{II}, and (○) Na^I.

than those in the dehydrated state. In both the states the absolute densities decrease for the pure resin. This is due to more close packing in the pure resin. The attrition effect of the various samples decreases from sample A to H, and this is due to the formation of the resin in the capillaries of charcoal particles.

The exchange capacities are higher for divalent ions than Na⁺ at the same concentration. The sizes of the hydrated Mg^{II}/Zn^{II}/Ca^{II} ions and Na^I ions are comparable. The higher exchange capacity for the divalent cations is due to the ionic charge. Among the divalent cations the exchange capacity increases from Mg^{II} to Ca^{II}. This may be due to the decrease in the hydrated ionic sizes from Mg^{II} to Ca^{II}. The exchange capacities are plotted against the percentage of sulphonated charcoal in the resin for the ions (Fig. 1). The exchange capacity decreases slowly upto 30% of the charcoal, and thereafter there is a sudden decrease. This indicates that the formation of the resin with more than 30% charcoal is not possible, hence the low exchange capacity. Thus it may be concluded that the substitution of charcoal upto 30% is highly economical.

References

1. KUNIN, "Ion Exchange Resins", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1958.
2. P. VASUDEVAN and N. L. N. SHARMA, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1979, 23, 1443.